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Mutual Classification of Legal and Moral Norms

Shavkat Khaknazarov

Independent researcher at the Higher School of Judges

Abstract. *This article analyzes the mutual classification of legal norms and moral norms. Most importantly, attention is paid to issues related to respect for the honor and dignity of persons involved in criminal proceedings. The article analyzes both national and foreign legislation, as well as the opinions of scientists.*

Keywords: *Constitution, criminal procedure, court, legal norms, moral norms, spirituality, reforms, ethics, justice, behavior, rights, and freedoms.*

Introduction

This article analyzes the mutual classification of legal norms and moral norms, examining the views of scholars in comparison with legislative norms. The fundamental changes occurring in Uzbek society are reflected in the elevation of moral values.

In her research, T.N. Moskalkova compared criminal procedural norms with moral norms.¹ She emphasized that the differences between criminal procedural rules and morality primarily stem from the fact that the norms of criminal procedural law are mandatory for participants in the criminal process, with their enforcement and compliance ensured through coercion. These norms are adopted, amended, and revoked by specially established legislative bodies. In contrast, moral norms, according to societal views, are unwritten, lacking the same meaning and binding force for all individuals. Ethical norms in the context of investigating and resolving criminal cases are chiefly a product of the official's consciousness, continuously emerging and evolving through people's practical activities. Their existence is not tied to the will of the legislator or other legislative entities. Criminal procedural norms apply equally to all members of society, whereas moral norms do not. The binding force of moral norms is derived from public example, public opinion, the influence of collective custom, and other forms of expressing societal will.

If we analyze the above-mentioned opinion, it appears to align with the views of T.N. Moskalkova. However, we disagree with these opinions. Today, compliance with ethical norms is mandatory, and

¹ Москалькова Т. Н. Нравственные основы уголовного процесса. Дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. Москва – 1997. 45 с.

failure by officials to adhere to the code of ethics may result in disciplinary action or termination of the employment contract. For instance, according to Article 18 of the Code of Judicial Conduct, if judges or court staff violate the provisions of the Code of Judicial Conduct or undermine the authority of the judiciary or the reputation of the judge, this situation provides grounds for disciplinary liability in the prescribed manner.² In addition, each organization has adopted a code of ethical norms. The regulatory documents adopted by these organizations are mandatory for all employees, and thus carry binding force. Norms of morality are also reflected in codes and laws. For example, Article 22 of the Criminal Procedure Code enshrines the principle of establishing truth.³ We all know that this term belongs not to the legal category, but to the moral category. According to Article 1 of the Code of Judicial Conduct, judges determine the rules of etiquette and conduct that a judge should follow in their professional activities related to the administration of justice, as well as during extracurricular time.⁴ Therefore, this norm obliges employees to comply with it during their professional activities, and possibly in their off-time activities. Continuing her opinion, T.N. Moskalkova stated that moral norms in the field of investigation and resolution of criminal cases are primarily a product of the consciousness of an official. If we focus on the content of Article 85 of the Criminal Procedure Code, it implies the collection of evidence that reveals legal, substantiated, and fair circumstances to prove the guilt or innocence of a person in order to establish the truth. The legislator calls on the investigator and judge to conscientiously fulfill their official and professional duties and to exhibit proper culture in determining the circumstances crucial for the fair resolution of a criminal case. Adherence to ethical requirements, principles, and prohibitions based on ideas of justice and humanity, duty, and conscience, are among the primary criteria for the professional suitability of an investigator, inquiry officer, prosecutor, and judge.

At the same time, Article 455 of this Code states that the verdict must be justified and fair. Indeed, every prosecuting body or judge is obligated to assess the evidence in accordance with their internal beliefs, following the law and legal consciousness, based on a comprehensive, complete, and impartial consideration of the circumstances when examining the case (Article 95 of the Criminal Procedure Code).⁵ It is evident that T.N. Moskalkova's views are primarily analyzed from a philosophical perspective.

In our opinion, today moral norms do not lose their moral characteristics within the content of legal norms, but rather enhance the significance of legal norms. Every case must be evaluated both from the perspective of law and justice. Moreover, ethical norms urge investigators and judges to be impartial and fair in handling cases. Furthermore, by incorporating moral norms into legal norms, the legislator shapes relationships that align with the interests of a comprehensive, complete, and impartial examination of all aspects of criminal proceedings.

According to T. Moskalkova, moral norms in criminal proceedings are divided into the following: a) those not directly enshrined in the legislation regulating criminal procedural activities; b) those reflected in acts

² Code of Judicial Conduct, approved by the Resolution of the Supreme Judicial Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 15, 2024, No. 1903.

³ The Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent, 2023.

⁴ Code of Judicial Conduct, approved by the Resolution of the Supreme Judicial Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 15, 2024, No. 1903.

⁵ The Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent, 2023.

of a non-normative legal nature (such as codes of etiquette); and c) those enshrined in criminal procedural legislation.⁶

Now, we will classify these categories:

1. Indeed, although moral norms are not directly reflected in some criminal procedural legislation, they are embedded in the essence and content of the legislation. For example, Article 2 of the Criminal Procedure Code outlines the main tasks of criminal procedural legislation. While these tasks do not explicitly reflect moral norms, one of the key objectives of the legislation is to impose on prosecuting authorities and the court the obligation to determine the **truth** of the case.⁷

2. Regarding the second category, moral norms are reflected in documents of a non-normative legal nature, including various ethical⁸ or etiquette⁹ codes. Before becoming a judge, each prospective judge takes an oath. Among the obligations voluntarily undertaken, the judge pledges to respect and uphold the rights and freedoms of individuals and citizens (Article 2, Paragraph 4, Code of Judicial Conduct).

The matter falling under the third category directly reflects moral norms within the framework of legislation. For instance, Article 12 of the Criminal Procedure Code mandates that a search of a person suspected of a crime and the seizure of items or other objects related to the crime must be carried out with the participation of an employee or witnesses of the same sex as the individual being searched. Furthermore, in accordance with Part 2 of Article 196 of this Law, if the taking of a sample from a suspect or accused involves undressing, the specialist conducting the procedure and all other individuals present must be of the same sex as the person being sampled.¹⁰ Additionally, it is stipulated that those involved in criminal proceedings must uphold the honor and dignity of all persons associated with the criminal case. The legislator expressly prohibits the use of torture, threats, coercion, mistreatment, and the adoption of actions or decisions that discriminate against a person (such as a suspect or witness) or undermine their honor and dignity (Article 17 of the Criminal Procedure Code).

According to D. Bazarova, the issue of respecting the honor and dignity of an individual within the criminal procedural sphere is of paramount importance. This area of legal relations is distinguished by the application of the most severe forms of state coercion and intrusion into the private lives of citizens. Liability for violating the principle of respect for a person's honor and dignity is addressed by criminal law (Article 235 of the Criminal Code).¹¹

The relationship between criminal procedural and moral norms continuously evolves in response to the historical development of society and the political changes within the state. Indeed, following the end of the Khanate period in Central Asia and the transition to a new socialist system, significant transformations occurred in both state governance and the legal framework. In place of Turkestan, a new socialist

⁶ Москалькова Т. Н. Нравственные основы уголовного процесса. Дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. Москва – 1997. 9 с.

⁷ The Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent, 2023.

⁸ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 595, dated October 14, 2022, "On Additional Measures to Ensure Adherence to Etiquette Standards by State Civil Servants

⁹ Code of Judicial Conduct, approved by the Resolution of the Supreme Judicial Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 15, 2024, No. 1903.

¹⁰ The Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent, 2023.

¹¹ Базарова Д.Б. Процессуальные гарантии прав личности в уголовном процессе. На соискание ученой степени доктора юридических наук (DSc). ТГЮУ. 2022. – С. 66-68.

Uzbekistan emerged. Subsequently, as a result of prolonged political, economic, and social struggles, Uzbekistan attained independence.¹² The legal system of Uzbekistan is part of the Roman-Germanic family of law. Overall, the legal systems of the CIS countries are modeled on the Russian legal system. In 1994, the Republic of Uzbekistan began adopting national codes and laws, including the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As a result of the judicial and legal reforms implemented in recent years, significant changes have taken place in criminal procedural legislation, particularly in relation to moral norms. This is most notably reflected in the institution of witness immunity.

It can be observed that moral norms are introduced in Part 4 of Article 28 of the new edition of the Constitution. For example, “No one is obliged to testify against himself or his close relatives (husband, wife, parents, brothers, sisters, etc.).”¹³ The rules enshrined in this norm are a classic example of the mutual harmony between moral and legal norms, as exposing testimony among close relatives can lead to the deterioration of relationships, thus contradicting moral principles.

In the criminal procedure legislation of the socialist period, this was not considered from a moral perspective; in practice, the testimony of the accused’s close relatives as witnesses in a criminal case was a painful choice, as refusing to testify against the accused often resulted in the relatives being labeled as criminals.

According to A.Pulatov, immunity is primarily an additional right granted to *certain categories* of individuals participating in criminal proceedings to safeguard their rights and legitimate interests. That is, it manifests itself in the objective of not disrupting social relations between close relatives. After all, providing information about the circumstances that expose the guilt of the suspect, accused, or defendant by their close relatives can harm their future relationships. Therefore, the legislator introduces this procedural rule and encourages those conducting criminal proceedings to employ other methods and means of proof.¹⁴ For example, when examining criminal cases in which the suspect, accused, or defendant's close relatives exercised their right to testify, it was observed that in such cases, the parents, spouse, brothers, or sisters of the suspect, accused, or defendant provided testimony regarding circumstances related to them.¹⁵ In this regard, it should be noted that the majority of the witnesses examined (as well as the victims)¹⁶ –approximately 90% – were not informed by the questioning authorities about their rights, particularly the necessity of obtaining their consent when being questioned, as well as when their close relatives were questioned regarding circumstances related to them.

It is precisely for this reason that, in the criminal materials examined, it became apparent that in many cases, testimony incriminating the accused was provided by close relatives. This observation was confirmed by 82% of the respondents who participated in the survey.

¹² On August 31, 1991, based on the Declaration of Independence, the Law “On the Fundamentals of State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan” was enacted.

¹³ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 2023.

¹⁴ Pulatov A.S. The Status of a Witness in Criminal Proceedings and Issues of Its Improvement: Autoreferat of Dissertation... Tashkent State University of Law, 2022. - pp. 59-65.

¹⁵ The study analyzed 110 criminal cases investigated by the investigative department of the Tashkent City Criminal Court and the Tashkent City Prosecutor’s Office.

¹⁶ During the study, investigators from the investigative department of the Internal Affairs Department of Tashkent city and 145 criminal cases under investigation by the investigative department of the Prosecutor's Office of Tashkent city were examined on a competitive basis.

Thus, scholars have proposed various perspectives on the interdependence of legal norms and moral norms. At the same time, moral norms in criminal procedural legislation manifest in the following ways: 1) they are not directly enshrined in the legislation regulating criminal procedural activities; 2) they are recognized in acts of a non-normative legal nature (such as codes of etiquette); and 3) they are enshrined in criminal procedural legislation. By comparing the moral norms across these three categories, it becomes evident that moral norms are reflected in almost all aspects of criminal procedural norms.

For instance, Article 2 of the Criminal Procedure Code mandates that prosecuting bodies are tasked with establishing the truth; Article 17 underscores the importance of respecting the dignity of individuals; Article 22 emphasizes the principle of establishing the truth; Article 19 calls for closed court sessions when private life details or information that may tarnish a person's honor and dignity are involved; Article 23 enshrines the presumption of innocence, which protects an individual's honor and reputation, especially if they are acquitted by higher courts; Article 455 asserts that a verdict must be lawful, reasonable, and fair; and Article 95¹ stipulates that evidence obtained through pressure or threats is inadmissible and etc.

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